

EMPLOYEES COMMITMENT AND GUEST PATRONAGE FOR 5-STAR HOTEL SERVICES.

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Keywords:

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Abstract: *The aim of this study was to identify the extent of relationship between employee's commitment and guest patronage for 5-star hotel services. The independent variable is measured through employee attitude to work, employees attitude to guests, employees skills, employees good human relationship, know if employees availability and accessibility, and employees prompt delivery of services to guests. To realise this, this research was carried out with six 5-star hotels located within the central business district area of the Federal Capital Territory Abuja. This research is designed in a descriptive approach with observation and questionnaire as sources of primary data. A population of 780 guests in these 5-star hotels were observed within two weeks with a sample size of 264, a structured questionnaire was distributed to the guests according to the percentage of population contributed by the selected 5-star hotels. The questionnaire was distributed through a convenience sampling technique. Data obtained was analysed through descriptive and inferential statistics, while the multiple regression analysis model was used to test the hypothesis. Findings from the study reveals that employee's commitment measured through employees attitude to job, employees attitude to guests, employees skill, employees good human relationship, employees availability and accessibility to guests, and employees prompt delivery of guests requests have significant relationship with guest's patronage for 5-star hotel services. Based on this, this study recommends that 5-Star Hotel management should train their employees regularly to ensure they have adequate skills for services in the hotel, to exhibit good attitude and good relationship with guest, and to always be available to attend to guest. This study has given adequate insight on the application and implication of employee's commitment on guest's patronage for 5-Star hotel services. Similar studies can be executed in major cities like*

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Lagos and Port Harcourt where the population comprise mainly of investors and business people, unlike Abuja that is predominantly politicians and civil servants.

Introduction

The main resources needed by every organization to perform efficiently and effectively are land, employees, capital and entrepreneurship (Rodgers, 1992). Among these resources, the employees are considered the most important of all. This is because, other resources are operated by the employees. Even the entrepreneur that initiate the innovation that metamorphoses into the business organization is engineered by the employees (Divanna & Rogers, 2005). The implication of this is that no organization can perform effectively and efficiently or has the capability of realizing her organizational goals and objectives without the firm commitment of the employees. Employees constitute the workforce in all the levels (Guest, 1997). Employee commitment is the affection and positive attitude an employee has over his job. Employee commitment can be described further as employee's effective communication which represents an employee's constructive emotional bonding to the organization (Aziz, 2021). Employee commitment is also an instrument that drives the employee to develop an emotional quotient which is mainly routed to employee's perception that it is costlier to lose the membership of an organization (Gardi, et.al, 2020). Some of the factors that could be responsible to employee commitment in an organization include: salary, bonus and other special benefits and compensation, job security, safety working environment, pension and gratuity, image of the organization, strong product brand, and good relationship with customers (Prabhu, et al, 2020).

A hotel is a business organization where guest patronize for accommodation, relaxation,

leisure, entertainment and sporting. Also, a hotels is a tool used to provide hospitality and leisure to guest. Hotels are categorised according to the level of luxury they provide for guests. A 5-Star Hotel is that class of Hotels that that provide luxury services through all its operations (Madu & Iweka, 2014). The aim of a 5-star Hotel is to offer desired services guests bat the highest level. The implication of the definitions of a good hotel is that every good hotel must have the ability to offer luxury, hospitality and leisure to customers. This can be achieved through committed employees (Kotler, et.al, 2003). It is only when a guest acquires these anticipated luxury, hospitality and leisure that the guest could be said to be satisfied. Guest satisfaction determines guest repeat patronage for the hotel.

Therefore, to achieve guest's satisfaction and repeat patronage, a 5-star hotel must deliver services to the guests at the highest level. This means that everything about the hotel from the exterior to the table should display excellent quality and high attention. Most 5-star hotels experience short life span because of the inability of the employees to realize the philosophy behind a 5-star hotel. Rather, the management of these 5-star hotels have embarked on expensive media promotions and production of Directories, yet the needed philosophy of a 5-star hotel which culminates with guests satisfaction is unrealizable. Studies by Nwosu, 2022; Adeola & Ezenwafor, 2020; Kukogi & Iwuagwu, 2021; and Mbuthia & Muchina, 2020, confirm that employee commitment is paramount to guest satisfaction in 5-star hotel services. Employee commitment can be measured through employee's attitudes to work, employees attitude to guest, employees skills, employee good human

relationship, employees availability and accessibility to guest and employees prompt delivery of guests request.

Research Objectives

The aim of this study is to identify the extent of relationship between employee's commitment and guest patronage for 5-star hotel services. Other objectives include to:

1. ascertain the nature of impact that employee attitude to work have on guests patronage for 5-star hotel services.
2. know how employees attitude to guests affect guests patronage for hotel services.
3. Identify the relationship between employees skills and guests patronage for 5-star hotels services.
4. discover the degree of relationship between employees good human relationship and guests patronage for 5-star hotel services.
5. know if employees availability and accessibility affect guests patronage for 5-star hotel services.
6. discover if employees prompt delivery of guest requests affect guests patronage for 5-star hotel services.

Research Question

What is the nature of relationship between employee's commitment and guest's patronage for 5-star hotel services?

Research Hypothesis

Employees Commitment has no significant relationship with Guests patronage for 5-star hotel services.

Concept of Employee Commitment

A well-defined service culture is preceded with employee's commitment to deliver the service. Employee in a hotel is the link between the service and the execution of the excellent service. This means that service can only be delivered through the employees. Variables that need to be considered under this include: employee attitude to work; employee attitude to guest; employees

skill and competence; effectiveness of human resources process; availability and accessibility of employees; and employees experience and skill on the services and the service delivery system.

It is important to further stress that the ability of the hotel to realize its objective of customer (guest) satisfaction depends on the productivity of the employees in the hotel. Lussier (2006) states that the employee's ability to work successfully in an organization determines the employee's productivity. This also measures the ability of the employee to adapt and operate in accordance to the service or corporate culture of the organization. Employee's behavior can be predicted through his/her personality, perception and attitude (Lussier, 2006). In addition to understanding the personality, perception and attitude of employees, the nature of customer-oriented services demands that employees in a highly service oriented product like a five star hotel must be persons adequately trained in their skills and how to deliver their services. That means skills in their chosen profession, and skills in delivering academic services to students for adequate satisfaction.

Customer satisfaction and patronage.

Customer value can be described as the difference between the actual or measurable benefits that the customer gets from owning or using a product and the actual costs of obtaining the product (Futrell, 2003). In a 5-star hotel, luxury, leisure and time is the most fascinating nonmonetary cost to customers. It is improper to expect an executive guest to queue in a line to book for a room, or expect him/her to wait for more than the time promised to deliver a meal or laundry service. These are factors that constitute value to customers in 5-star hotels.

Customer satisfaction is the ability of the company to satisfy customer needs. Kotler et.al., 2006 state that customer satisfaction depend on

product-perceived performance in delivering value compared to customers expectation. If the product's performance falls short of customer's expectation, the buyer is dissatisfied; if the performance matches the expectation, the buyer is satisfied; but if performance exceeds expectation, the buyer is delighted. Jobber, 2004 therefore recommends that smart companies should aim to delight customers by promising what they can deliver and striving to deliver more than they have promised.

The marketing concept established the fact that the customer is the king (Brassington and Pettitt: 2006). This means that, until the customer is satisfied, all efforts for service delivery is a waste. Copley, 2017 identifies six (6) reasons why customer satisfaction is important, these reasons include: it is an indicator of customers' repeat purchase and patronage or loyalty; it is used as a key differentiator among competing organizations; it is used to avoid customers' agitation over an organizations' service; it increases customers lifeline value (CLV) which is also an increase in revenue accruable to the service organization; customer satisfaction reduces negative word of mouth by the customer against the organization; and it enables the organization retain existing customers which is cheaper than acquiring new ones.

Theoretical Review and Framework

Theory of Customer Expectation

The theory of customer expectation is a very popular theory used in describing the nature of satisfaction derived from a product by a consumer. Baska, 2021 states that the structure of the theory was developed by Richard L. Oliver in 1977 and 1980 after two series of studies. This theory seeks to give explanations to post-purchase and post-adoption satisfaction as a function of expectation, perceived performance and disconfirmation of beliefs. The popularity of the theory is linked to the extent that most

scholars modify the name and explanations. Some of these names are disconfirmation theory and expectation disconfirmation theory. In further elaboration, Baska, 1992 states that the philosophy of the Expectation theory beliefs that a consumer satisfaction or dissatisfaction is a result of the consumer comparison of performance of a product with already set standards of performance, and that the possible outcomes can emanate from that belief. These outcomes include; Positive disconfirmation which results when performance is perceived by consumer to be better than the anticipated expectations, thus causing the consumer to be delighted; zero disconfirmation which result when performance is perceived to be exactly equal to expectation, thus causing the consumer to be likely satisfied; and negative disconfirmation which results when the performance is lower than the consumer's expectation, thus causing the consumer to be dissatisfied. This theory is related to our study because the philosophy of the theory is based on consumer satisfaction based on past experience.

Empirical Review

'A Review of the Hotel Industry in Nigeria: Size, structure and issues' was executed by Nwosu, B. in 2016 and published in worldwide hospitality and tourism themes, 8 (2) Pages 117-133.

The propose of this study is to provide an overview of the dynamics that define, govern and shape the tourism and hospitality sector in Nigeria in particular the hotel industry with respect to its size, structure and salient issues that impact on it. Primary survey data from STR Global was used. Also, content analysis of secondary data from government education and industry sources were used to identify the issues within the industry.

Major findings from the study show: positive indicators for employment and further

expansion within the hotel sector in Nigeria; the lack of supporting institutions, legal framework and industry representation makes the management of human resources an area of concern. The study recommends the need for a research agenda for the hospitality and tourism industry in Nigeria. This will further create the framework to understand and improve best practices particularly with institutional framework, employments and human capital development.

This study is relevant to our study as it emphasizes the need for human capital development which is currently lacking in the Nigeria hotel business and which is part of the objectives of the study.

'Promotional Activities in Hotels: Applications in The Turkey's Region of Cappadocia' was carried out by Acar, N., Gullu, R., and Karamustafa, K. and published in 2012 in *Prose Dea-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 58 Pages 1027-1036.

This study was aimed at evaluating the promotional activities used by hotels and expected benefits from them. Relevant data was collected through questionnaire from the 252 employees of the hotel operating in the region of Cappadocia in Turkey. Data obtained were analyzed using ANOVA. The result from data and analysis indicate that there are enormous benefits from promotional activities by the hotels. Based on this, the study recommends that sustainable efforts should be maintained on promotional activities for successful hotel business. The study is relevant to our study because it recognizes the importance of promotions to improving the quality of hotel services which is also a proxy to our study.

'Customer Service Experience in Hotel Operations: An Empirical Analysis', was carried out by Khan, I., Ruchi J.G., and Rahman, Z., and published 2015 in *Proceda-Social and Behavioral Sciences* 189 Pages 266-274.

This study was aimed at bringing an understanding of customers experience quality in hotel operations. The study adopted customer experience scale and examined its effect on customer satisfaction, brand loyalty and word of mouth in the hotel industry. The primary data was obtained from 326 hotel guests from Waridivar and Dehradum Districts in India through a questionnaire. The questions were anchored on customer experience quality scale, loyalty, customer satisfaction and word of mouth. Data obtained were tested through regression model. The major findings confirm that there is positive and significant influence of all four customer experience quality (EXQ) dimensions on consumer behavioral outcomes; that customer evaluation is not only based on service encounters, but also includes every touch point with an organization; and that customer experience has effect on customers patronage as a behavioral outcome. The study therefore advocates collective efforts by all employees of a service organization to ensure a positive experience by the customer. The study is related to our study because customers experience is one of the determinants of customer patronage for a hotel and is one of the major pillars of our study.

Existing Gaps for the Study

The observed gaps from the literature reviewed for this study include that little emphasis have been given to the relevance of employees commitment on guest patronage for 5-star hotels in the hotel industry. Also, little emphasis have been given to grading for hotel services despite the fact that grading is a determinant factor for customer expectation from hotel services.

Methodology

This research was carried out with six 5-star hotels located within the central business district area of the Federal Capital Territory Abuja. This research is designed in a descriptive approach

with observation and questionnaire as sources of primary data. A population of 780 guests in these 5-star hotels were observed within two weeks with a sample size of 264, a structured questionnaire was distributed to the guests according to the percentage of population contributed by the selected 5-star hotels. The questionnaire was distributed through a convenience sampling technique. 260 (98.48%) of the distributed questionnaire were properly filled and returned. Data obtained was analysed through descriptive and inferential statistics,

Respondents Gender

Table 4.2:GENDER

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	208	80.0	80.0	80.0
	Female	52	20.0	20.0	100.0
	Total	260	100.0	100.0	

Source:SPSS Output (Based on questionnaires” Data 2023).

From table 4.2 above, it is obvious that out of the 260 copies of questionnaire retrieved, female respondents answered 52 copies which indicates

while the multiple regression analysis model was used to test the hypothesis.

Data Analysis and Result

This section is devoted to the analysis of data collected for the purpose of this study, and the interpretation of the various result arrived at from the analysis.

Analysis of Demographic Variables

The analyses in this section concern data related to: gender, country of residence, age of respondents, and occupation of respondents.

20% of the respondents; while male respondents answered 208 copies which represents 80% of the total respondents.

Residence of Respondents

Table 4.3:COUNTRY OF RESIDENCE

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Nigeria	208	80.0	80.0	80.0
	Outside Nigeria	52	20.0	20.0	100.0
	Total	260	100.0	100.0	

Source:SPSS Output (Based on questionnaires” Data 2023).

Table 4.3 shows the analysis of country of residence of the respondents. It reveals that 208 which represent 80% frequency reside in Nigeria

while 52 of our respondents representing 20% reside outside Nigeria.

Age Bracket of Respondents

Table 4.4:AGE BRACKET

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	<20yrs	2	.8	.8	.8
	20-30yrs	50	19.2	19.2	20.0
	31-40yrs	104	40.0	40.0	60.0
	41-50yrs	52	20.0	20.0	80.0

51yrs above	52	20.0	20.0	100.0
Total	260	100.0	100.0	

Source:SPSS Output (Based on questionnaires” Data 2023).

Table 4.4 shows age bracket of respondents out of which 2 persons representing 0.8% are under 20 years. Age bracket within 20-30yrs answered 50 copies representing 19.2% of the respondents; age bracket 31-40 answered 104 copies which

indicate 40% of the respondents, age bracket 41-50 answered 52 copies representing 20% while respondents of 51yrs and above answered 52 copies representing 20% of the total respondents

Occupation of Respondents

Table 4.5: OCCUPATION OF RESPONDENTS

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Provisional self employed	100	38.5	38.5	38.5
Industrialist, Investors or4 Trader	4	1.5	1.5	40.0
Public or Civil Servant	52	20.0	20.0	60.0
Politician	104	40.0	40.0	100.0
Total	260	100.0	100.0	

Source:SPSS Output (Based on questionnaires” Data 2023).

The occupation of respondents was analyzed in table 4.5. The analysis shows that respondents who are self-employed answered 100 copies which represent 38.5%; industrialist, investors or traders answered 4 copies representing 1.5%; public and civil servants answered 52 copies representing 20% while politicians answered 104 copies representing 40% of total respondents.

Univariate Analysis

This section is primarily concerned with the analysis of univariate variables relating to the respondents’ views on the questions contained in the research question. The primary analysis entailed the assessment of the distribution and applications of statistical analysis on each variable as a means of examining the tendencies of these variables. The research instrument generated data that showed the degree of

agreement of the major variable, as well as the dimensions and measures.

The data obtained from the field was measured using a 5-point Likert scale based on Very High Extent(VHE) /Strongly Agree (SA) (5); High Extent (HE) /Agree (A) (4); Moderate Extent (ME) /Undecided (UD) (3); Low Extent (LE) /Disagree (DIS) (2) and Very Low Extent(VLE) /Strongly Disagree (SD) (1). As such interpretations for each variable is premised on the extent to which it’s mean distributions reflect either significant evidence (where $x > 3.0$) or the extent to which it reflects insignificant evidence (where $x < 3.0$).

Research Question

To what extent can employee’s commitment impact on guest’s satisfaction for hotel services?

Table 4.20: Computation of Mean Responses on the impact of Employee’s Commitment on guest patronage for Hotel Services in Abuja
Descriptive Statistics

Indicators	N	Min	Max	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
EMPLOYEES COMMITMENT	260	1.00	5.00	1100.14	4.2313	.57495	.331
You are satisfied with the Employees Commitment of this hotel, and based on this you are willing to maintain patronage for the hotel.	260	1	5	1074	4.13	.547	.299
You are satisfied with the employee's attitude to work in this hotel, and based on this you are willing to maintain your patronage for the hotel.	260	1	5	1168	4.49	.748	.560
You are satisfied with the employee's attitude to guest in this hotel, and based on this you are willing to maintain your patronage for the hotel.	260	1	5	1222	4.70	.659	.435
You are satisfied with the employee's skills and competence in this hotel, and based on this you are willing to maintain your patronage for the hotel.	260	1	5	1073	4.13	.559	.312
You are satisfied with the employee's good human relations in this hotel, and based on this you are willing to maintain your patronage for the hotel.	260	1	5	1073	4.13	.559	.312
You are satisfied with the employee's availability and accessibility in this hotel, and based on this you are willing to maintain your patronage for the hotel.	260	1	5	1073	4.13	.559	.312
You are satisfied with the employees prompt delivery of guest request in this hotel, and based on this you are willing to maintain your patronage for the hotel.	260	1	5	1016	3.91	.781	.609
Valid N (listwise)	260						

Source: SPSS output (Base on questionnaires' data 2023)

Table 4.20 illustrates the summary of the analysis from statistics on the impact of employee's commitment on guest's patronage for hotels service with summarized values for central tendency based on the responses to the indicators. The analysis revealed that all indicators on the scale had mean scores above the criterion mean of 3.00 on a 5-point likert scale which was accepted by the researcher. With the grand mean of 4.23 the respondents agreed that employee's commitment's impacts on customer satisfaction of hotels service in Abuja is to a high extent.

Test of Hypotheses

Table 4.23: Cohen et al statistical correlation decision scale frame

S/N	Statistical Significance	Association
i.	0.1 – 0.29	Very Weak
ii.	0.3 – 0.49	Weak
iii.	0.5 – 0.69	Moderate
iv.	0.70 – 0.79	Strong
v.	0.80 – 1.00	Very strong

Source: Cohen et al (2007)

Cohen et al (2007) posit that, effect size is an easy way to quantify both relationship and difference between two groups and at the same time to measure the effectiveness and statistical significance. Generally, the decision rule for the acceptance or rejection of hypothetical statements is premised on the adoption of a 0.05 significance threshold due to its 95% test on all hypotheses. Similarly, for the purpose of ease of presentation analysis and interpretation understanding, the researcher's proposed hypothesis is thus grouped into those relating to employees commitment and guests patronage for hotel services.

If the probability value (PV) is greater than 0.05 alpha level, we accept the null hypothesis of no significant relationship. The data is thus analysed below.

Testing for Hypothesis

The bivariate relationship determination in this section was done using Simple Linear Regression in the assessment of the relationship between the dimensions of employees commitment and guests patronage for 5-star hotel services.

Thus, in determining the respective strength and statistical relationship of the association between these variables, the researcher was guided by the work of Cohen et al. (2007). The coefficient of correlation (effect size) the strength of association and statistically significant decision according to Cohen, et al. (2007) is interpreted below.

The formulae:

$$Y = a + bX + \epsilon$$

Where:

Y – Dependent variable

X – Independent (explanatory) variable

a – Intercept

b – Slope

ε – Residual (error)

Decision Rule

If the probability value (PV) in the coefficient table is less than 0.05 alpha level, we Reject the null hypotheses and accept the alternate hypotheses of significant relationship.

Table 4.26: Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.963 ^a	.927	.927	.17982	.185

a. Predictors: (Constant), EMPLOYEES COMMITMENT

b. Dependent Variable: GUESTS PATRONAGE

Source: SPSS output (2023)

Table 4.26 provides the *R* and *R*² values. The *R* value represents the simple correlation and is 0.963^a (the "**R**" Column), which indicates a high degree of correlation. The *R*² value (the "**R Square**" column) indicates that 96.3% of the total variation in the dependent variable, Guests patronage, can be explained by the independent

variable, Employee's Commitment which is very large. The Durbin-Watson "d" = .185, is between the two critical values of 1.5 < d < 2.5 and therefore we can assume that there is no first order linear auto-correlation in the data. Hence the model is of absolute good fit.

Table 4.27: ANOVA

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	105.981	1	105.981	3277.626	.000 ^b
	Residual	8.342	258	.032		
	Total	114.323	259			

a. Dependent Variable: GUESTS PATRONAGE

b. Predictors: (Constant), EMPLOYEES COMMITMENT

Source: SPSS output (2023)

The probability value of 0.000 indicates that the regression relationship was significant in determining how Employee's Commitment impact on Guests Patronage for hotels service. The *F* calculated at 5 percent level of significance was 3277.626. Since *F* calculated is greater than

the *F* critical (value = 2.4472), this shows that the overall model was significant. Also the *p* < 0.000, is less than 0.05, and indicates that, overall, the regression model statistically significantly predicts the outcome variable (i.e., it is a good fit for the data).

Table 4.28: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	.592	.083		7.129	.000
	EMPLOYEES COMMITMENT	1.113	.019	.963	57.251	.000

a. Dependent Variable: CUSTOMER SATISFACTION

Source: SPSS output (2023)

The regression result in table 4.28 shows a model constant (a) value of 0.592 and Employee's Commitment value of 1.113, indicating that, for every one percent increase in Employee's Commitment, the dependent variable 'Guests Patronage' will rise by 100%. T-value produced 7.129, is significant at P value (.000), which is less than the chosen alpha of α (0.05). Thus, the hypothesis which states that, there is no significant relationship between employee's commitment and guest's patronage for 5-star hotel services in Abuja is rejected. Thus a very strong significant relationship exists between employee's commitment and Guests patronage for 5-star hotel services in Abuja.

Findings

Based on the analysis of data, and result of hypothesis testing, the study reveals that Employee's commitment measured through employees attitude to job, employees attitude to guests, employees skill, employees good human relationship, employees availability and accessibility to guests, and employees prompt delivery of guests requests have strong significant linear relationship with guest's patronage for 5-star hotel services.

Conclusion

The research findings have provided answer to the research questions, and also provided solutions the research objectives which aimed at identifying the relationship between employee's commitment and guest's patronage for 5-star hotel services. This is based on the revelation that Employee's commitment measured through employees attitude to job, employees attitude to guests, employees skill, employees good human relationship, employees availability and accessibility to guests, and employees prompt delivery of guests requests have strong significant linear relationship with guest's patronage for 5-star hotel services.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion, this study recommends that 5-Star Hotel management should train their employees regularly to ensure they have adequate skills for services in the hotel, to exhibit good attitude and good relationship with guest, and to always be available to attend to guest.

Contribution to Knowledge

This study has given adequate insight on the application and implication of employee's commitment on guest's patronage for 5-Star hotel services.

Suggestion for further Studies

It is suggested that a similar study be executed in major cities like Lagos and Port Harcourt where the population comprise mainly of investors and business people, unlike Abuja that is predominantly politicians and civil servants.

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